

METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING EDUCATIONAL WORK BASED ON INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Abstract: In this article, we describe the nature of interactive teaching methods and learning in the organization of students, socio-cultural activities, other pedagogic, self-learning and from there to a higher level.

Key words: Methodology of educational work, method, interactive method, educational technology, methodology, education, upbringing, knowledge, student.

Main part: The importance of the educational process in the development of society is incomparable. In this, it is necessary to educate a person, to encourage him to acquire knowledge, to work, and to gradually turn these actions into skills, to form basic competencies. Today, the modern education model leads to observing the free thinker in the society. And this helps in educating people who have life goals and who know their worth. Education and training regularly develop and update in accordance with the times. In this place, training of competent personnel who can demonstrate all the equipment of professional life receives continuous education. In this pedagogic higher education article, methodical recommendations on loading interactive technologies in the teaching of the subject "Methodology of educational work" are given. Pedagogy makes the discipline of "Methodology of educational works" highly educational in the spiritual and moral education of higher education students. Because through this subject, the student will have the ability to organize educational production in further pedagogical activities.

The methodology of educational work is a methodology that involves managing the organization of practices to produce the products necessary for students to become

useful individuals and society. This methodology aims to provide students with the necessary knowledge and skills in spirituality, literature, creativity, being useful to society, creative activities, sports, art and other fields.

The following key points are highlighted in this methodology:

Individual characteristics and special needs of students: Each student should be educated according to his personal characteristics, educational level and abilities. In the methodology, attention should be paid to the individual needs of students.

Practical learning: Students should be given more practical training to acquire theoretical knowledge. This method will be very useful for students to absorb and implement the information.

Interactive learning: Students should be motivated to acquire knowledge through the use of interactive textbooks, multimedia materials, and interactive activities.

Defining goals: The goal and future outcomes of each practice are clear to students and give them a purposeful approach.

Implementation of learned knowledge: Practical training and creative activities should be organized to implement the knowledge that students are learning.

Cooperation with parents, pedagogues and other educational forces: In the methodology, parents and pedagogues are important for the acquisition and development of students. Students are motivated by their strength and support

The term "interactive method" has the same meaning as "interactive learning" or "active learning" method. In this methodology, students are motivated to acquire knowledge through dynamic hands-on activities and interactive tutorials. Students can learn, absorb and apply information through this method.

✚ The main feature of the interactive method is to inspire the students to participate actively. In this method, the student is introduced to interactive textbooks, multimedia materials, interactive exercises and creative activities to obtain information.

✚ The interactive method is very useful for students to enhance their understanding, learn and apply the information. Students reinforce information through this method by participating in learning, asking questions, and asking for advice.

✚ In addition, the interactive method is very useful for the development of students' creative activities. It is possible to develop students' creative abilities by asking them for advice, giving feedback, organizing creative activities and other interactive practices.

✚ The advantage of the interactive method is that it creates more inspiration, motivation and interest in the students as a result of their active participation in the process of receiving and learning information. This accelerates students' learning and development.

Conclusion: Based on this method, students develop the qualities of patriotism, loyalty to national and universal values, politeness, modesty, and self-spiritual, spiritual, intellectual, and creative development, striving for perfection, and alternative evaluation of one's own behavior. and the ability to make independent decisions, to be kind to people and to believe in universal and national values, to follow cultural rules, to have a culture of dealing in relationships is developed

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